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THE POWER OF SCIENCE HANDS-ON ACTIVITIES

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Science education is regarded as a remnant of substance and fact-based knowledge in today's educational system. It improves learners scientific and analytical abilities as well as their ethical values and attitudes. To properly address the learning demands of the learners, adequate and appropriate teaching methods should be utilized. Teaching is not just about imparting knowledge from textbooks or curricula; it also includes effective lesson delivery that fosters learners' participation. In order to help the learners to learn effectively and creatively in the new era of pedagogical change, teachers must employ the right approaches and concepts. A useful educational institution depends on its teachers, who are effectively transfer knowledge to learners. The ability of teachers to innovate teaching strategies is an essential aspect in determining the learning experiences' quality.

Through engaging and observing activities, students actively and effectively learn. The learning process is significantly accelerated when an actual application is incorporated and the learner benefits from the applied knowledge and skills. When the unique characteristics of students in this age range are taken into account, developing practical skills in learners may seem like a challenging task. They are extremely inquisitive, enthusiastic, and restless, and they make use of all of their senses to interpret their surroundings. The K-12 science curriculum has begun modifying the Philippine educational system. The present curriculum encourages science teachers to assist learning using various methods and to create a learner-centered, inquiry-based environment in each classroom (K-12 Science Curriculum Guide, 2013). In the context of recent scientific and technological breakthroughs, science education is crucial. According to the Ministry of National Education of Turkey (2013), the goal of science education is to aid students in strengthening their scientific literacy. More so, students need to develop scientific inquiry skills while learning scientific facts and principles. In inquiry-based learning environments, students are more active and they are guiding their own learning processes.

Students learn new information, apply the concepts they have been taught, and may come up with a workable solution to a problem through practical exercises. Hands-on activities motivate an interest of lifelong learning and drive students to explore and learn new things. Learners are more likely to understand and retain the material being taught when they are actively involved in hands-on activities. In addition, the most useful solutions are to trigger students' interest and optimize their active involvement and, therefore, their engagement in the learning process. Utilizing instruments and tools that can help make abstract knowledge more real and understandable, activity-based learning strategies have been promoted as a way to improve learners' understanding of scientific process. Further,

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hands-on approach is the best way to teach since it allows students to learn through experiential learning. Meaningful information can be regarded as experiential if it somehow links to the learner's previous experiences, whether directly or indirectly. Therefore, meaningful experiences can be ensured when the principles of learning by doing are applied to the spontaneous actions of learners' experiences.

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